

COMPARATIVE STUDY OF FLAT SLAB AND CONVENTIONAL SLAB USING ETABS

J AHILA JOHNSY¹, M KATHIRVEL NAREN², Dr.SURESH BABU.S³

Department of Civil Engineering, Adiyamaan College of Engineering, Hosur.

Assistant professor, Department of Civil Engineering, Adiyamaan college of Engineering, hosur.

Head of the Department of Civil Engineering, Adiyamaan college of Engineering, Hosur.

ABSTRACT: In this thesis, the structural behavior of both flat slab and conventional slab in multi-storied building is to be compared. The rapid growth of the urban population and the consequent pressure on limited space has considerably influenced multi-storied building construction. . Two main groups according to the arrangement of slabs, beams or girders, and columns are Framed Structure and flat slab structure. This multi-storied building structure will be analyzed not only considering the vertical loads (dead load & live load), it also includes lateral load (earthquake load). Earth quake loads will be considered for all different zones in India .Structural modeling & analysis will be done using ETABS software.

Key word: Flat slab, Framed structure, Multi-storied building, Vertical load, Local load, Earthquake load, ETABS software.

I. INTRODUCTION

Slab is a flat two dimensional planar structural element having thickness small compared to its other two dimensions. It provides a working flat surface or a covering shelter in buildings. It primarily transfers the load by bending in one or two directions. Reinforced concrete slabs are used in floors and roofs of buildings. Conventional slabs are supported on monolithic concrete beams and columns as framed structure system (or) it can be directly supported by walls. The flat slabs are only supported by columns when used in the areas where more space and floor height required. Flat slab is a reinforced concrete slab supported

directly by concrete columns without the use of beams.

Flat Slabs are considered suitable for most of the construction and for asymmetrical column layouts like floors with curved shapes and ramps etc. The advantages of applying flat slabs are many like depth solution, flat soffit and flexibility in design layout. Even though building flat slabs can be an expensive affair but gives immense freedom to architects and engineers the luxury of designing. Benefit of using flat slabs are manifold not only in terms of prospective design and layout efficacy but is also helpful for total construction process especially for easing off installation

procedures and saving on construction time. If possible, try to do away with drop panels as much as possible and try to make the best use of thickness of flat slabs.

Drop panels and column heads are used above the column to give support and increase the shear strength of the slab.

II. **BENEFITS OF USING FLAT SLAB:**

- Flexibility in room layout
- Saving in building height
- Shorter construction time
- Ease of installation of M&E services
- Use of prefabricated welded mesh
- Buildable score

III. **SCOPE OF THE PROJECT:**

- Flat slabs are effective systems for multi storied buildings without beams but these slabs are not commonly employed in Indian conditions.
- Predicting the behaviour of flat slabs and conventional slabs under seismic loads using Seismic co-efficient Method and Response spectrum method.
- It will provide sufficient information and confidence

to go for flat slabs in future construction in India.

IV. **OBJECTIVE OF THE PROJECT:**

- To study the structural performance of flat slab and conventional slab structure subjected to various loads and conditions.
- To the study the behavior of both structures for the parameters likes lateral displacement, story drift.
- Comparison of flat slab and conventional slab in RCC building for the above said parameters

V. **LITERATURE REVIEW**

- **Dynamic Analysis of Multistory RCC Building Frame with Flat Slab and Grid Slab - Ravi Kumar Makode, Saleem Akhtar, Geeta Batham (2014)**

The rapid growth of the urban population and the consequent pressure on limited space has considerably influenced multi- building storied construction. With increase in demand for space, construction of multi-storied buildings is becoming a necessary part of our living style. These multi-storied buildings can be constructed using various structural systems. Two main

groups according to the arrangement of slabs, beams or girders, and columns are Framed Structure and flat slab structure. Framed structures are the structure having the combination of beams, columns and slabs to resist the lateral and gravity load. These structures are usually used to overcome the large moments developing due to the applied loading. The flat slab buildings in which slab is directly rested on columns, have been adopted in many buildings constructed recently due to the advantage of reduced floor to floor heights to meet the economical and architectural demands.

- **Lateral load analysis of R.C.C. Building - Kevadkar, Kodag (2013)**

This thesis studied the responses of R.C.C. building to earthquake for three cases. These cases are I) RC building frame without bracing and shear wall, II) RC building frame with different shear wall system, III) RC building frame with Different bracing system. Analysis is done by using ETABS .It is found that the X type of steel bracing system significantly contributes to the

structural stiffness and reduces the maximum inter story drift, lateral displacement and demand capacity (Performance Point) of R.C.C building than the shear wall system.

- **Analysis and Evaluation of Structural systems with bracings - Anil baral, Yajdani (2015)**

Investigated the response of building with different positioning of shear wall using both Equivalent Static Method (Seismic Coefficient Method) and Response spectrum Analysis, Five different Model of RCC building, one with no shear wall and other four models with different position of shear wall which is subjected to earthquake load in zone V has been studied .This study also incorporates how the bending moment, shear force for beam and axial Force for column vary with change in positioning of RC shear wall. Building are modelled and analysed using standard package ETABS.

VI. METHODOLOGY:

First stage :

Study of the project

Review of literature

Preliminary design data collection

Second stage :

- Load calculations
- Modelling using ETABS
- Structural analysis

Third stage :

- Result verification
- Comparisons and discussion

Conclusion

VII. STRUCTURAL MODELING

The modeling, computer aided analysis of the models under study is done using Three Dimensional Analysis of Buildings and Structures software ETABS.

G+18 storey RCC buildings are taken for this project. The building has plan dimensions of (30 m x 18 m). The size of slab panel is 6m x 6m and the storey height is 3.6m in the entire floor including the ground Floor. M30 grade concrete and Fe415 structural steel is used. In seismic weight calculations, 25 % of the floor live loads are considered. G+18 storey RCC buildings with conventional slab and flat slab are analyzed. The buildings adopted consist of reinforced concrete and brick masonry elements. The frames are assumed to be firmly fixed at the bottom and the soil- structure interaction is neglected.

Table 1.1 Design Data

DESCRIPTI ON	CONVEN TIONAL SLAB	FLAT SLAB
No. of Stories	G+18	G+18
Plan area of the building	30 m x 18 m	30 m x 18 m
Typical storey height	3.6 m	3.6 m
Total height of building	64.8 m	64.8 m
Slab panel size	6 m x 6 m	6 m x 6 m
Slab thickness	200 mm	300 mm
Beam size taken	0.3 m x 0.75 m	-
Column size taken	0.6 m x 0.6 m	0.6 m x 0.6 m
Soil type	Medium	Medium
Earthquake zones	II, III, IV & V	II, III, IV & V
Importance factor, I	1.5	1.5
Response reduction	5	5

factor		
Grade of concrete	M30	M30
Grade of steel	Fe415	Fe415
Support conditions	Fixed	Fixed

Load considerations:

3-D model is prepared with the above specifications for the Static and Dynamic analysis of the building in ETABS. The dead, live and earthquake load considerations that are taken into account are explained in detail.

Table 1.2 DEAD AND LIVE LOADS

Loads	Convention al slab	Flat slab
Live load	3.0 kN/m ²	3.0 kN/m ²
Floor finish	1.0 kN/m ²	1.0 kN/m ²
Wall load	13.2 kN/m	13.2 kN/m

LOAD COMBINATIONS:

1.5(DL+LL)

1.2(DL + LL ± EQX)

1.2(DL + LL ± EQY)

1.5(DL ± EQX)

1.5(DL ± EQY)

0.9DL ± 1.5 EQX

0.9DL ± 1.5 EQY

1.2(DL + LL ± RSX)

1.2(DL + LL ± RSY)

1.5(DL ± RSX)

1.5(DL ± RSY)

0.9DL ± 1.5 RSX

0.9DL ± 1.5 RSY

Where EQX & EQY and RSX & RSY are lateral force obtained from static analyses and Response spectrum analyses in X and Y direction respectively.

CONVENTIONAL SLAB:

In a G+18 RC building, 200 mm thickness of conventional slab is provided in all stories. The height of each storey is 3.6m including the base storey. The width of the wall is 6 m in all directions and it’s provided from the base to the top storey of building. Rigid diaphragm is assigned for all floors.

Fig .1.1 Plan layout of conventional slab

Fig .1.2 3D view of conventional slab

FLAT SLAB

In a G+18 RC building, 300 mm thickness of flat slab is provided in all stories. The centre to centre spacing between the columns is given as 6m. The height of each storey is 3.6m including the base storey. The width of the wall is 6 m in all directions and it's provided from the

base to the top storey of building. Rigid diaphragm is assigned for all floors.

Fig 1.3 Plan layout of flat slab

Fig 1.4 View of flat slab

RESULT AND DISCUSSIONS

The analysis is run and the necessary data such as maximum storey drift and displacement of the structure are taken into account for comparison and the maximum storey displacement variations, all zone values in the buildings are also

compared. From the seismic analysis, the results obtained in X and Y directions are illustrated. The result are found for two methods such as,

- Seismic co-efficient method
- Response spectrum method

STOREY DRIFT:

Storey drift is the displacement of one level relative to other level above or below. It was checked whether the structure satisfies maximum permissible relative lateral drift criterion as per IS: 1893-2002 (Part-I) which is 0.004H for both shear wall and steel bracing systems.

Displacement for Conventional & Flat slab for Zone II (X -Direction):

(Seismic co-efficient method)

Storey	Conventional slab	Flat slab
(No)	(mm)	(mm)
19	29.322	35.495
18	28.768	34.89
17	27.999	34.023
16	27.021	32.892
15	25.857	31.526
14	24.531	29.953
13	23.066	28.201
12	21.482	26.295

11	19.8	24.261
10	18.038	22.123
9	16.215	19.9
8	14.347	17.615
7	12.448	15.283
6	10.532	12.924
5	8.611	10.55
4	6.698	8.176
3	4.801	5.816
2	2.936	3.497
1	1.166	1.332

Displacement for Conventional & Flat slab for Zone II (Y -Direction):

(Seismic co-efficient method)

Storey	Conventional slab	Flat slab
(No)	(mm)	(mm)

19	32.4	48.836
18	31.604	47.842
17	30.594	46.512
16	29.377	44.843
15	27.979	42.867
14	26.422	40.62
13	24.732	38.14
12	22.93	35.463
11	21.037	32.621
10	19.075	29.647
9	17.063	26.57
8	15.018	23.419
7	12.958	20.219
6	10.898	16.993
5	8.853	13.763
4	6.834	10.551
3	4.856	7.383
2	2.937	4.317
1	1.146	1.564

Storey	Conventional slab	Flat slab
(No)	(mm)	(mm)
19	46.915	56.792
18	46.028	55.824
17	44.799	54.437
16	43.234	52.628
15	41.372	50.442
14	39.25	47.925
13	36.905	45.121
12	34.371	42.072
11	31.68	38.818
10	28.861	35.396
9	25.944	31.841
8	22.955	28.183
7	19.916	24.454
6	16.851	20.678
5	13.778	16.88
4	10.716	13.082
3	7.681	9.306
2	4.698	5.595
1	1.866	2.131

Displacement for Conventional & Flat slab for Zone III (X -Direction):

(Seismic co-efficient method)

Displacement for Conventional & Flat slab for Zone III (Y -Direction):

(Seismic co-efficient method)

Storey (No)	Conventional slab (mm)	Flat slab (mm)
19	51.84	78.138
18	50.566	76.548
17	48.95	74.418
16	47.004	71.749
15	44.766	68.587
14	42.276	64.993
13	39.571	61.025
12	36.687	56.74
11	33.66	52.193
10	30.521	47.435
9	27.301	42.512
8	24.029	37.47
7	20.733	32.35
6	17.437	27.188
5	14.164	22.021
4	10.935	16.882
3	7.77	11.813

2	4.699	6.907
1	1.834	2.502

Displacement for Conventional & Flat slab for Zone IV (X -Direction):

(Seismic co-efficient method)

Storey (No)	Conventional slab (mm)	Flat slab (mm)
19	70.372	85.188
18	69.043	83.736
17	67.199	81.655
16	64.851	78.942
15	62.058	75.663
14	58.876	71.887
13	55.358	67.681
12	51.557	63.108
11	47.52	58.227
10	43.292	53.094
9	38.917	47.761
8	34.432	42.275
7	29.874	36.68
6	25.276	31.017

5	20.667	25.32
4	16.074	19.623
3	11.521	13.959
2	7.046	8.393
1	2.799	3.196

9	40.951	63.768
8	36.044	56.205
7	31.1	48.525
6	26.156	40.783
5	21.246	33.032
4	16.403	25.323
3	11.655	17.719
2	7.048	10.36
1	2.75	3.754

Displacement for Conventional & Flat slab for Zone IV (Y -Direction):
(Seismic co-efficient method)

Storey (No)	Conventional slab (mm)	Flat slab (mm)
19	77.759	117.206
18	75.849	114.822
17	73.425	111.628
16	70.505	107.623
15	67.149	102.881
14	63.414	97.489
13	59.356	91.537
12	55.031	85.11
11	50.489	78.29
10	45.781	71.152

Displacement for Conventional & Flat slab for Zone V (X -Direction):
(Seismic co-efficient method)

Storey (No)	Conventional slab (mm)	Flat slab (mm)
19	105.558	127.782
18	103.564	125.604
17	100.798	122.483
16	97.276	118.413

15	93.087	113.495
14	88.313	107.831
13	83.037	101.522
12	77.335	94.662
11	71.28	87.341
10	64.938	79.641
9	58.375	71.641
8	51.648	63.413
7	44.812	55.021
6	37.914	46.525
5	31.001	37.98
4	24.111	29.434
3	17.282	20.938
2	10.569	12.59
1	4.198	4.794

Storey	Conventional slab	Flat slab
(No)	(mm)	(mm)
19	116.639	175.809
18	113.773	172.232
17	110.137	167.442
16	105.758	161.435
15	100.724	154.321
14	95.121	146.234
13	89.035	137.306
12	82.546	127.666
11	75.734	117.435
10	68.671	106.728
9	61.427	95.652
8	54.066	84.308
7	46.65	72.787
6	39.234	61.174
5	31.87	49.548
4	24.604	37.984
3	17.482	26.578
2	10.572	15.54
1	4.125	5.63

Displacement for Conventional & Flat slab for Zone V (Y -Direction):
(Seismic co-efficient method)

Displacement for Conventional & Flat slab for Zone II (X -Direction):

(Response spectrum method)

Storey	Conventional slab	Flat slab
(No)	(mm)	(mm)
19	13.818	16.793
18	13.588	16.547
17	13.278	16.202
16	12.887	15.756
15	12.423	15.217
14	11.894	14.594
13	11.304	13.89
12	10.657	13.112
11	9.957	12.265
10	9.209	11.353
9	8.414	10.379
8	7.577	9.346
7	6.699	8.26
6	5.783	7.122
5	4.83	5.935
4	3.838	4.697
3	2.807	3.409
2	1.746	2.084
1	0.702	0.803

Displacement for Conventional & Flat slab for Zone II (Y -Direction):

(Response spectrum method)

Storey	Conventional slab	Flat slab
(No)	(mm)	(mm)
19	13.818	16.793
18	13.588	16.547
17	13.278	16.202
16	12.887	15.756
15	12.423	15.217
14	11.894	14.594
13	11.304	13.89
12	10.657	13.112
11	9.957	12.265
10	9.209	11.353
9	8.414	10.379
8	7.577	9.346
7	6.699	8.26
6	5.783	7.122
5	4.83	5.935

4	3.838	4.697
3	2.807	3.409
2	1.746	2.084
1	0.702	0.803

8	12.123	14.954
7	10.718	13.215
6	9.253	11.395
5	7.728	9.496
4	6.14	7.516
3	4.491	5.454
2	2.794	3.335
1	1.123	1.285

Displacement for Conventional & Flat slab for Zone III (X -Direction):

(Response spectrum method)

Storey (No)	Conventional slab (mm)	Flat slab (mm)
19	22.108	26.869
18	21.742	26.476
17	21.245	25.923
16	20.619	25.209
15	19.877	24.348
14	19.03	23.35
13	18.086	22.225
12	17.051	20.98
11	15.932	19.624
10	14.734	18.164
9	13.463	16.606

Displacement for Conventional & Flat slab for Zone III (Y -Direction):

(Response spectrum method)

Storey (No)	Conventional slab (mm)	Flat slab (mm)
19	24.284	36.454
18	23.737	35.803
17	23.057	34.95
16	22.25	33.891
15	21.331	32.639
14	20.312	31.206
13	19.204	29.605

12	18.014	27.85
11	16.749	25.952
10	15.416	23.921
9	14.021	21.767
8	12.568	19.498
7	11.063	17.123
6	9.508	14.651
5	7.904	12.093
4	6.249	9.456
3	4.544	6.749
2	2.803	4.016
1	1.111	1.475

16	30.928	37.814
15	29.815	36.522
14	28.545	35.025
13	27.129	33.337
12	25.577	31.47
11	23.898	29.436
10	22.101	27.246
9	20.194	24.909
8	18.184	22.431
7	16.077	19.823
6	13.879	17.093
5	11.592	14.244
4	9.211	11.273
3	6.736	8.181
2	4.191	5.002
1	1.685	1.927

Displacement for Conventional & Flat slab for Zone IV (X -Direction):

(Response spectrum method)

Storey (No)	Conventional slab (mm)	Flat slab (mm)
19	33.162	40.304
18	32.612	39.714
17	31.867	38.885

Displacement for Conventional & Flat slab for Zone IV (Y -Direction):

(Response spectrum method)

Storey	Conventional slab	Flat slab
(No)	(mm)	(mm)
19	36.427	54.682
18	35.605	53.705
17	34.585	52.425
16	33.374	50.837
15	31.996	48.958
14	30.468	46.809
13	28.806	44.408
12	27.02	41.775
11	25.123	38.928
10	23.124	35.881
9	21.032	32.65
8	18.852	29.247
7	16.594	25.684
6	14.261	21.976
5	11.856	18.139
4	9.374	14.184
3	6.815	10.123
2	4.205	6.025
1	1.666	2.212

Displacement for Conventional & Flat slab for Zone V (X -Direction):

(Response spectrum method)

Storey	Conventional slab	Flat slab
(No)	(mm)	(mm)
19	49.743	60.456
18	48.919	59.57
17	47.801	58.328
16	46.392	56.721
15	44.723	54.782
14	42.817	52.537
13	40.693	50.005
12	38.365	47.205
11	35.847	44.154
10	33.152	40.87
9	30.291	37.364
8	27.276	33.647
7	24.116	29.734
6	20.819	25.639
5	17.387	21.366
4	13.816	16.91
3	10.105	12.271
2	6.286	7.503
1	2.527	2.891

5	17.783	27.208
4	14.06	21.276
3	10.223	15.184
2	6.307	9.037
1	2.499	3.318

Displacement for Conventional & Flat slab for Zone V (Y -Direction):

(Response spectrum method)

Storey (No)	Conventional slab (mm)	Flat slab (mm)
19	54.64	82.023
18	53.407	80.558
17	51.878	78.638
16	50.062	76.255
15	47.994	73.437
14	45.702	70.213
13	43.208	66.612
12	40.53	62.663
11	37.685	58.392
10	34.686	53.822
9	31.547	48.975
8	28.279	43.87
7	24.891	38.526
6	21.392	32.964

Storey drift for Conventional & Flat slab for Zone II (X -Direction):

(Seismic co-efficient method)

Storey (No)	Conventional slab	Flat slab
19	0.000154	0.000168
18	0.000214	0.000241
17	0.000272	0.000314
16	0.000323	0.00038
15	0.000368	0.000437
14	0.000407	0.000487
13	0.00044	0.000529
12	0.000467	0.000565
11	0.000489	0.000594
10	0.000506	0.000617

9	0.000519	0.000635
8	0.000528	0.000648
7	0.000532	0.000656
6	0.000533	0.000659
5	0.000532	0.000659
4	0.000527	0.000656
3	0.000518	0.000644
2	0.000492	0.000604
1	0.000325	0.000371

13	0.000501	0.000744
12	0.000526	0.00079
11	0.000545	0.000826
10	0.000559	0.000855
9	0.000568	0.000876
8	0.000572	0.000889
7	0.000572	0.000896
6	0.000568	0.000897
5	0.000561	0.000892
4	0.00055	0.00088
3	0.000533	0.000854
2	0.000497	0.000772
1	0.00032	0.000435

Storey drift for Conventional & Flat slab for Zone II (Y -Direction):

(Seismic co-efficient method)

Storey (No)	Conventional slab	Flat slab
19	0.000221	0.00028
18	0.000281	0.00037
17	0.000338	0.000464
16	0.000389	0.000549
15	0.000432	0.000624
14	0.00047	0.000689

Storey drift for Conventional & Flat slab for Zone III (X -Direction):

(Seismic co-efficient method)

Storey (No)	Conventional slab	Flat slab
19	0.000246	0.000269

18	0.000342	0.000386
17	0.000435	0.000503
16	0.000517	0.000607
15	0.000589	0.000699
14	0.000651	0.000779
13	0.000704	0.000847
12	0.000748	0.000904
11	0.000783	0.000951
10	0.00081	0.000988
9	0.000831	0.001016
8	0.000844	0.001036
7	0.000852	0.001049
6	0.000854	0.001055
5	0.000851	0.001055
4	0.000843	0.001049
3	0.000829	0.001031
2	0.000787	0.000966
1	0.00052	0.000594

	slab	
(No)		
19	0.000354	0.000448
18	0.000449	0.000592
17	0.000541	0.000742
16	0.000622	0.000879
15	0.000692	0.000999
14	0.000751	0.001103
13	0.000801	0.001191
12	0.000841	0.001264
11	0.000872	0.001322
10	0.000894	0.001368
9	0.000909	0.001401
8	0.000916	0.001423
7	0.000916	0.001434
6	0.000909	0.001436
5	0.000897	0.001428
4	0.000879	0.001409
3	0.000853	0.001366
2	0.000796	0.001234
1	0.000511	0.000696

Storey drift for Conventional

& Flat slab for Zone III (Y - Direction):

(Seismic co-efficient method)

Storey	Conventional	Flat slab
--------	--------------	-----------

Storey drift for Conventional & Flat slab for Zone IV (X -Direction):

(Seismic co-efficient method)

Storey (No)	Conventional slab	Flat slab
19	0.000369	0.000404
18	0.000513	0.000579
17	0.000652	0.000754
16	0.000776	0.000911
15	0.000884	0.001049
14	0.000977	0.001169
13	0.001056	0.001271
12	0.001121	0.001356
11	0.001174	0.001426
10	0.001215	0.001482
9	0.001246	0.001524
8	0.001266	0.001554
7	0.001277	0.001573
6	0.00128	0.001583
5	0.001276	0.001583
4	0.001265	0.001573
3	0.001243	0.001546
2	0.00118	0.001449
1	0.000781	0.000891

Storey drift for Conventional & Flat slab for Zone IV (Y -Direction):

(Seismic co-efficient method)

Storey (No)	Conventional slab	Flat slab
19	0.000531	0.000672
18	0.000674	0.000888
17	0.000811	0.001113
16	0.000932	0.001318
15	0.001038	0.001499
14	0.001127	0.001654
13	0.001202	0.001786
12	0.001262	0.001895
11	0.001308	0.001984
10	0.001342	0.002052
9	0.001363	0.002101
8	0.001373	0.002134
7	0.001373	0.002151
6	0.001364	0.002153
5	0.001346	0.002142
4	0.001319	0.002113

3	0.00128	0.002049
2	0.001194	0.001852
1	0.000767	0.001044

7	0.001916	0.00236
6	0.00192	0.002374
5	0.001914	0.002374
4	0.001897	0.00236
3	0.001865	0.00232
2	0.00177	0.002174
1	0.001171	0.001336

Storey drift for Conventional & Flat slab for Zone V (X -Direction):
(Seismic co-efficient method)

Storey drift for Conventional & Flat slab for Zone V (Y -Direction):
(Seismic co-efficient method)

Storey (No)	Conventional slab	Flat slab
19	0.000554	0.000605
18	0.00077	0.000869
17	0.000978	0.001131
16	0.001164	0.001367
15	0.001326	0.001574
14	0.001466	0.001753
13	0.001584	0.001906
12	0.001682	0.002034
11	0.001761	0.002139
10	0.001823	0.002223
9	0.001869	0.002286
8	0.001899	0.002331

Storey (No)	Conventional slab	Flat slab
19	0.000796	0.001008
18	0.001011	0.001332
17	0.001217	0.00167
16	0.001399	0.001978
15	0.001557	0.002248
14	0.001691	0.002481
13	0.001802	0.002679
12	0.001892	0.002843

11	0.001962	0.002975	13	0.000212	0.000257
10	0.002012	0.003078	12	0.000225	0.000273
9	0.002045	0.003152	11	0.000235	0.000288
8	0.00206	0.003201	10	0.000245	0.000301
7	0.00206	0.003227	9	0.000254	0.000313
6	0.002046	0.00323	8	0.000263	0.000325
5	0.002018	0.003213	7	0.00027	0.000336
4	0.001978	0.00317	6	0.000276	0.000344
3	0.00192	0.003073	5	0.000282	0.000353
2	0.001791	0.002778	4	0.000289	0.000362
1	0.00115	0.001566	3	0.000295	0.000369

2	0.00029	0.000357
1	0.000196	0.000224

Storey drift for Conventional & Flat slab for Zone II (X -Direction):

(Response spectrum method)

Storey (No)	Conventional slab	Flat slab
19	0.000077	0.000088
18	0.000112	0.000131
17	0.000143	0.000169
16	0.000166	0.000198
15	0.000184	0.00022
14	0.000199	0.000239

Storey drift for Conventional & Flat slab for Zone II (Y -Direction):

(Response spectrum method)

Storey (No)	Conventional slab	Flat slab
19	0.000108	0.000141
18	0.000143	0.00019

17	0.000174	0.000235
16	0.000198	0.00027
15	0.000216	0.0003
14	0.00023	0.000327
13	0.000242	0.000351
12	0.000253	0.000372
11	0.000262	0.000391
10	0.000269	0.000408
9	0.000276	0.000423
8	0.000282	0.000437
7	0.000287	0.000451
6	0.000291	0.000462
5	0.000295	0.00047
4	0.000299	0.000476
3	0.000303	0.000477
2	0.000294	0.000446
1	0.000194	0.000256

	slab	
(No)		
19	0.000123	0.000142
18	0.000179	0.00021
17	0.000228	0.000271
16	0.000266	0.000317
15	0.000295	0.000352
14	0.000319	0.000382
13	0.00034	0.000411
12	0.000359	0.000437
11	0.000377	0.00046
10	0.000392	0.000481
9	0.000407	0.000501
8	0.00042	0.00052
7	0.000432	0.000537
6	0.000442	0.000551
5	0.000451	0.000564
4	0.000463	0.000579
3	0.000473	0.000591
2	0.000464	0.000572
1	0.000313	0.000358

Storey drift for Conventional & Flat slab for Zone III (X -Direction):

(Response spectrum method)

Storey	Conventional	Flat slab
--------	--------------	-----------

Storey drift for Conventional & Flat slab for Zone III (Y -Direction):

(Response spectrum method)

Storey (No)	Conventional slab	Flat slab
19	0.000173	0.000226
18	0.000229	0.000304
17	0.000279	0.000376
16	0.000317	0.000432
15	0.000345	0.00048
14	0.000368	0.000523
13	0.000387	0.000562
12	0.000404	0.000596
11	0.000419	0.000626
10	0.000431	0.000653
9	0.000442	0.000678
8	0.000452	0.0007
7	0.000459	0.000721
6	0.000465	0.000739
5	0.000471	0.000752
4	0.000479	0.000762
3	0.000485	0.000764
2	0.00047	0.000713
1	0.00031	0.00041

Storey drift for Conventional & Flat slab for Zone IV (X -Direction):

(Response spectrum method)

Storey (No)	Conventional slab	Flat slab
19	0.000184	0.000212
18	0.000268	0.000315
17	0.000342	0.000407
16	0.000399	0.000475
15	0.000442	0.000528
14	0.000478	0.000573
13	0.00051	0.000616
12	0.000539	0.000656
11	0.000565	0.00069
10	0.000589	0.000721
9	0.00061	0.000751
8	0.00063	0.00078
7	0.000648	0.000805
6	0.000662	0.000826
5	0.000677	0.000846
4	0.000694	0.000868

3	0.000709	0.000886
2	0.000696	0.000858
1	0.00047	0.000537

10	0.000647	0.00098
9	0.000663	0.001016
8	0.000677	0.00105
7	0.000689	0.001082
6	0.000698	0.001108
5	0.000707	0.001128
4	0.000719	0.001143
3	0.000727	0.001146
2	0.000705	0.00107
1	0.000465	0.000615

Storey drift for Conventional & Flat slab for Zone IV (Y -Direction):

(Response spectrum method)

Storey (No)	Conventional slab	Flat slab
19	0.00026	0.000338
18	0.000344	0.000457
17	0.000418	0.000564
16	0.000475	0.000648
15	0.000518	0.00072
14	0.000552	0.000785
13	0.000581	0.000843
12	0.000606	0.000894
11	0.000628	0.000939

Storey drift for Conventional & Flat slab for Zone V (X -Direction):

(Response spectrum method)

Storey (No)	Conventional slab	Flat slab
19	0.000277	0.000318
18	0.000402	0.000473

17	0.000513	0.00061
16	0.000598	0.000713
15	0.000663	0.000791
14	0.000717	0.00086
13	0.000765	0.000924
12	0.000808	0.000984
11	0.000847	0.001035
10	0.000883	0.001082
9	0.000916	0.001127
8	0.000946	0.00117
7	0.000971	0.001208
6	0.000994	0.001239
5	0.001016	0.001269
4	0.001041	0.001302
3	0.001064	0.001329
2	0.001044	0.001287
1	0.000705	0.000806

Storey (No)	Conventional slab	Flat slab
19	0.00039	0.000508
18	0.000516	0.000685
17	0.000627	0.000846
16	0.000713	0.000972
15	0.000777	0.00108
14	0.000828	0.001178
13	0.000872	0.001265
12	0.00091	0.00134
11	0.000942	0.001409
10	0.00097	0.00147
9	0.000994	0.001525
8	0.001016	0.001575
7	0.001034	0.001622
6	0.001047	0.001662
5	0.001061	0.001692
4	0.001078	0.001715
3	0.001091	0.001719
2	0.001058	0.001605
1	0.000697	0.000923

Storey drift for Conventional & Flat slab for Zone V (Y -Direction):

(Response spectrum method)

CONSLUSION

The Lateral displacement of both conventional slab and Flat slab are having minimum at plinth level and maximum at terrace level, as the number of stories increases lateral displacement also increases. When compared to conventional slab, flat slab having more displacement in all seismic zones.

The lateral displacement of both conventional slab and flat slab are found out for seismic co-efficient method and response spectrum method and when comparing the displacement value obtained from seismic co-efficient method are greater than response spectrum method.

Storey drift is having minimum value at plinth, top stories and maximum at middle stories, thus extra stiffness of column requires at middle stories compared to other stories in both seismic

co-efficient method and response spectrum method.

REFERENCE

1. IS 875 (part 1): 1987, Dead loads, “Code of practice for Design loads (other than earthquake) for buildings and structures”, Bureau of Indian Standards, New Delhi.
2. IS 875 (part 2): 1987, Live loads, “Code of practice for Design loads (other than earthquake) for buildings and structures”, Bureau of Indian Standards, New Delhi.
3. IS 1893 (part 1): 2002, “Criteria for earthquake resistant design of structures”, Bureau of Indian Standards, New Delhi.
4. IS 456:2000, “Code of practice for plain and reinforced concrete”, Bureau of Indian Standards, New Delhi.
5. Kevadkar M.D, Kodag P.B, (2013), “Lateral Load Analysis Of R.C.C Building”, International Journal of Modern Engineering Research (IJMER) , Vol.3, Issue.3
6. Dynamic Analysis of Multistory RCC Building Frame with Flat Slab and Grid Slab - Ravi Kumar Makode, Saleem Akhtar, Geeta Batham (2014)

7. Comparative study of Flat slabs and Conventional RC slabs in High seismic zone – Manu K V, Naveen kumar B, Priyanka S (2014)
8. Comparative Study of Flat Slab and Conventional Slab Structure Using ETABS for Different Earthquake Zones of India – Mohana devi H.S, Kavan kumar M.R (2015)
9. Analysis and Evaluation of Structural systems with bracings - Anil baral, Yajdani (2015)